

Digital Intensity in Europe

It grew by 64.43% on average in the DESI Index countries between 2016 and 2021

As part of the Desi Index, the value of the Digital Intensity is calculated. Digital Intensity is made up of a set of indicators, namely:

- Use of ICT security measures;
- Make employees aware of their obligations in ICT "security matters";
- The contracted maximum download speed of the fastest Internet connection is at least 30 Mb / s;
- They use the ERP software package to share information;
- They use any social media;
- They use social media for any purpose;
- Use customer relationship management software-CRM;
- > 50% of employees use computers and the internet;
- > 20% of workers with portable devices for corporate use;
- Sell at least 1% of turnover online;
- Receive electronic orders (web or EDI) from customers in other EU countries
- 1% of total web sales and B2C web sales > 10% of web sales.

Then a percentage of the firms that have these characteristics is calculated. The percentage of companies that have these characteristics constitutes the value of digital intensity at the country level.

Ranking of countries by value of digital intensity in 2021. Denmark is in first place by value of digital intensity in Europe with a value of 12.68, followed by Finland with a value of 12.52 and Sweden with a value of equal to 11.33. In the middle of the table are Spain with a value of 7.47, followed by Germany and Croatia with a value of 7.43. Latvia closed the ranking with a value of 3.38 units, followed by Romania and Bulgaria with a value of 1.52 units.

Ranking of countries by percentage change in digital intensity in Europe between 2016 and 2021. Bulgaria ranks first in terms of the percentage change in digital intensity with a value of 8744.78% equal to an amount of 1.50 units, followed by Romania with a variation equal to an amount of 7425.04% equal to an amount of 1.50 and by Latvia with a growth equal to 133.04% equal to an amount of 1.93 units. And in the middle of the table there are Croatia with a value equal to 62.68% equal to an amount of 2.86 units, followed by Germany with a variation of 62.65% equal to an amount of 2.86 units, and Spain with a percentage change of 62.44% equal to an amount of 2.87 units. Sweden closes the ranking with a percentage change equal to an amount of 49.68% equal to an amount of 3.76 units, followed by Finland with a change equal to an amount of 47.55% equal to an amount of 4.03. units and from Denmark with a variation equal to an amount of 47.29% equal to a variation of 4.07 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. A clustering is carried out below using the k-Means algorithm optimized through the Silhouette coefficient. The indication of the following clusters derives from this, namely:

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- Cluster 1: Greece, Latvia, Hungary;
- Cluster 2: Estonia, Belgium, Netherlands, Malta, Italy;
- Cluster 3: Spain, Germany, Croatia, Austria, Luxembourg, Ireland, Czech Republic, Slovenia;
- Cluster 4: Finland, Denmark, Sweden;
- Cluster 5: Bulgaria, Romania;
- Cluster 6: Slovakia, Poland, Lithuania, Portugal, France, Cyprus.

By calculating the value of the median of the clusters it is possible to generate the following ordering, that is: $C4 = 12.52 > C2 = 9.73 > C3 = 7.58 > C6 = 5.44 > C1 = 3.75 > C5 = 1.52$. As is evident from the analysis, there is a contrast between Central Northern Europe and Central-Southern Europe with a particular setback of Eastern Europe. It follows that the need to aim for the growth of digitization should lead to the creation of European programs that are oriented towards upward convergence in the dissemination and application of technological knowledge.

Network analysis using the Manhattan distance. A network analysis is carried out below using the Manhattan distance. The analysis shows the presence of two complex network structures - i.e. with a number of linkages greater than 2 - and four simplified network structures with a number of linkages equal to 2. There is therefore a complex network structure constituted by Croatia, Austria, Luxembourg, Spain, and Germany. In particular, the following connections are detected, that is:

- Croatia has a connection with Austria with a link equal to 0.14 units, with Spain with a value equal to 0.024, and with Germany equal to 0.14;
- Austria has a connection with Croatia equal to a value of 0.14 units, and with Germany with a link equal to 0.14 units, with Luxembourg with a value equal to 0.11 units, and with Spain with a value of 0.12;
- Germany has a connection with Austria with a link having a value of 0.14, with Croatia with a value of 0.003, with Spain with a value of 0.02;
- Spain has a link with Germany equal to a value of 0.02 units, with Austria with a variation of 0.12 units, and with Croatia with a value of 0.024.
- Luxembourg has a connection with Austria with a link equal to an amount of 0.11 units.

Furthermore, a complex network structure is identified consisting of Slovakia, Poland, and Portugal, in particular:

- Slovakia has a connection with Poland with a link with a value of 0.072 units;
- Poland has a connection with Slovakia with a link with a value of 0.072 and with Portugal with a value of 0.086;
- Portugal has a connection with Poland with a link with a value of 0.086 units.

In addition, there are four simplified network structures, namely:

- There is a relationship between Finland and Denmark with a link equal to 0.089;
- Italy and Slovenia are united in a simple network structure with a value of 0.11;
- There is a connection between Belgium and the Netherlands with a link equal to 0.007;
- There is a relationship between Bulgaria and Romania with a value of 0.0022.

Conclusions. The analysis shows a significant growth in digital intensity in the countries analyzed by the DESI Index. However, it should also be considered that there is a significant difference between European countries in terms of digital intensity. The countries of Northern Europe are far ahead of

the countries of Southern and Eastern Europe. Europe needs to continue investing in digitization, above all because the "old continent" is far behind both China and the US. The technological and digital backwardness of the European Union could have a significant impact on the economic growth path of EU countries and could lead to a growing gap both towards the Atlantic area and towards high-tech Asian countries. In an economic system that consumes more and more technology to produce added value, technological innovation stops being a sub-topic for specialists, and becomes a main theme for long-term economic policies.

Declarations

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Appendix

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Austria	★ 4,7703	★ 5,5271	★ 5,5271	★ 6,7313	★ 7,2053	★ 7,6935
Belgium	★ 6,5474	★ 7,4418	★ 7,4418	★ 8,8651	★ 9,4253	★ 10,0023
Bulgaria	★ 0,0172	★ 0,4058	★ 0,4058	★ 1,0242	★ 1,2676	★ 1,5183
Croatia	★ 4,5668	★ 5,3078	★ 5,3078	★ 6,4869	★ 6,9510	★ 7,4291
Cyprus	★ 2,6020	★ 3,1908	★ 3,1908	★ 4,1278	★ 4,4966	★ 4,8765
Czechia	★ 4,1357	★ 4,8433	★ 4,8433	★ 5,9694	★ 6,4126	★ 6,8691
Denmark	★ 8,6119	★ 9,6662	★ 9,6662	★ 11,3440	★ 12,0043	★ 12,6845
Estonia	★ 6,3371	★ 7,2152	★ 7,2152	★ 8,6126	★ 9,1625	★ 9,7290
Finland	★ 8,4854	★ 9,5299	★ 9,5299	★ 11,1920	★ 11,8462	★ 12,5201
France	★ 3,4439	★ 4,0979	★ 4,0979	★ 5,1387	★ 5,5483	★ 5,9703
Germany	★ 4,5711	★ 5,3124	★ 5,3124	★ 6,4921	★ 6,9564	★ 7,4347
Greece	★ 1,7383	★ 2,2602	★ 2,2602	★ 3,0908	★ 3,4176	★ 3,7544
Hungary	★ 2,0259	★ 2,5700	★ 2,5700	★ 3,4360	★ 3,7769	★ 4,1279
Ireland	★ 5,1535	★ 5,9399	★ 5,9399	★ 7,1914	★ 7,6840	★ 8,1914
Italy	★ 5,5536	★ 6,3710	★ 6,3710	★ 7,6718	★ 8,1838	★ 8,7111
Latvia	★ 1,4508	★ 1,9504	★ 1,9504	★ 2,7455	★ 3,0584	★ 3,3808
Lithuania	★ 3,2393	★ 3,8775	★ 3,8775	★ 4,8930	★ 5,2927	★ 5,7044
Luxembou	★ 4,9201	★ 5,6884	★ 5,6884	★ 6,9112	★ 7,3924	★ 7,8881
Malta	★ 5,9496	★ 6,7976	★ 6,7976	★ 8,1473	★ 8,6784	★ 9,2256
Netherlan	★ 6,5573	★ 7,4524	★ 7,4524	★ 8,8769	★ 9,4376	★ 10,0151
Poland	★ 2,9319	★ 3,5462	★ 3,5462	★ 4,5239	★ 4,9087	★ 5,3050
Portugal	★ 2,8104	★ 3,4153	★ 3,4153	★ 4,3780	★ 4,7569	★ 5,1472
Romania	★ 0,0202	★ 0,4091	★ 0,4091	★ 1,0279	★ 1,2714	★ 1,5222
Slovakia	★ 3,0337	★ 3,6559	★ 3,6559	★ 4,6461	★ 5,0359	★ 5,4373
Slovenia	★ 5,3912	★ 6,1960	★ 6,1960	★ 7,4768	★ 7,9809	★ 8,5001
Spain	★ 4,6001	★ 5,3437	★ 5,3437	★ 6,5269	★ 6,9927	★ 7,4724
Sweden	★ 7,5711	★ 8,5447	★ 8,5447	★ 10,0942	★ 10,7040	★ 11,3322

Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	<i>Denmark</i>	12,68	14	<i>Croatia</i>	7,43
2	<i>Finland</i>	12,52	15	<i>Czechia</i>	6,87
3	<i>Sweden</i>	11,33	16	<i>France</i>	5,97
4	<i>Netherlands</i>	10,02	17	<i>Lithuania</i>	5,70
5	<i>Belgium</i>	10,00	18	<i>Slovakia</i>	5,44
6	<i>Estonia</i>	9,73	19	<i>Poland</i>	5,31
7	<i>Malta</i>	9,23	20	<i>Portugal</i>	5,15
8	<i>Italy</i>	8,71	21	<i>Cyprus</i>	4,88
9	<i>Slovenia</i>	8,50	22	<i>Hungary</i>	4,13
10	<i>Ireland</i>	8,19	23	<i>Greece</i>	3,75
11	<i>Luxembourg</i>	7,89	24	<i>Latvia</i>	3,38
12	<i>Austria</i>	7,69	25	<i>Romania</i>	1,52
13	<i>Spain</i>	7,47	25	<i>Bulgaria</i>	1,52
14	<i>Germany</i>	7,43			

Variazione Percentuale della Digital Intensity in Europa tra il 2016 ed il 2021.

Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Bulgaria</i>	1,50	8744,78	15	<i>Spain</i>	2,87	62,44
2	<i>Romania</i>	1,50	7425,04	16	<i>Austria</i>	2,92	61,28
3	<i>Latvia</i>	1,93	133,04	17	<i>Luxembourg</i>	2,97	60,32
4	<i>Greece</i>	2,02	115,98	18	<i>Ireland</i>	3,04	58,95
5	<i>Hungary</i>	2,10	103,76	19	<i>Slovenia</i>	3,11	57,67
6	<i>Cyprus</i>	2,27	87,41	20	<i>Italy</i>	3,16	56,86
7	<i>Portugal</i>	2,34	83,15	21	<i>Malta</i>	3,28	55,06
8	<i>Poland</i>	2,37	80,94	22	<i>Estonia</i>	3,39	53,53
9	<i>Slovakia</i>	2,40	79,23	23	<i>Belgium</i>	3,45	52,77
10	<i>Lithuania</i>	2,47	76,10	24	<i>Netherlands</i>	3,46	52,73
11	<i>France</i>	2,53	73,36	25	<i>Sweden</i>	3,76	49,68
12	<i>Czechia</i>	2,73	66,09	26	<i>Finland</i>	4,03	47,55
13	<i>Croatia</i>	2,86	62,68	27	<i>Denmark</i>	4,07	47,29
14	<i>Germany</i>	2,86	62,65				